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Questionnaire: Active learning - students' perspective

We are academics who are interested in the needs of current students. We want to understand better what the study process looks like through your eyes and what forms of work are best for you, so please answer the 9 questions below.

-----**The proper part of the survey.** Metrics will appear at the end of the survey.

1. What percentage of all classes are practical classes (all forms of classes other than lectures) during your current studies?

- 0%
- 1-50%
- More than 50%

2. Which activities do you participate in most willingly? (you can select only one value in a given column, please sort by importance, where 5 - most preferred, 1 - least preferred)

	1	2	3	4	5	0 - I don't know this form of classes/or least important/
Lectures						
Practicals						
Laboratories						
Conversation classes						
Project classes						
Seminars						

3. Which working methods/tools did you interact with during your studies (never, sometimes, often)?

	never	sometimes	often
Group work			
Discussions			
Reading articles			
Case studies			
Preparing papers (by students)			
Joint assessment of other students' work			
Making presentations (by students)			
Watching videos			
Recording films (by students)			
Field work			
Flipped classroom			
Other, which?			

Which working methods/tools did you interact with during your studies (never, sometimes, often)? **Other - which?** _____

4. Which of the listed methods/tools do you appreciate the most (choose max. 5)?

Group work	
Discussions	
Reading articles	
Case studies	
Preparing papers (by students)	
Joint assessment of other students' work	
Making presentations (by students)	
Watching videos	
Recording films (by students)	
Field work	
Flipped classroom	
Other [...]	

5. Mark those applications that have been used at least once in class (during your studies):

- Mentimeter
- Padlet
- Jamboard
- Squla
- Whiteboard
- Prezi
- Moodle
- Kahoot
- Canva
- Lucidchart
- Other.....

6. The perfect lecturer/academic is one who:

	not important	not very important	I have no opinion	important	very important
Has a high level of knowledge in the relevant area,					
Has practical experience in the relevant area,					
Engages students during class,					
Adds variety to the class (e.g. ...),					
Relates to students with respect,					
Treats students as partners.					
Is punctual (does not arrive late to class, turns in work on time, etc.).					
Is available (responds to messages, turns up for consultations, etc.).					

7. What difficulties did you experience during your studies? [multiple choice]

- No contact/ difficult contact with lecturer(s)
- Lecturer did not provide course materials

- Wrongly designed study programme (subjects in wrong order e.g. more advanced before basic subjects))
- Materials received from the lecturer are full of content, it is not clear what is important and what is not
- Lack of attendance of the lecturer at classes
- Provided content inconsistent with the course
- Other _____

8. In your opinion, the most important thing in effective teaching is for the teacher to:

- impart knowledge in a way that is understandable to the group
- create conditions for acquiring/developing skills
- create opportunities for students to develop social skills

9. How artificial intelligence affects studying (in your opinion)?

- does not impact
- provides new opportunities
- inspires
- dangerous (relieves students of 'thinking')

----- Metrics

Country: [listed]

Age (full years)

Year of study

Type of studies:

- Undergraduate studies (BA)
- Master's degree studies (MA)
- Long-cycle master's degree (MA)

Field of study (name of your field of study)